

Table 1. Grain yield and N uptake (grain + straw) of rice crop. ^a Pantnagar, U. P., India. 1987-90.

Treatment ^b	Grain yield (t/ha)			N uptake (kg/ha)		
	1987-88	1988-89	1989-90	1987-88	1988-89	1989-90
Control	3.9 a	2.9	2.7	56.4 a	49.8	47.8
PU @ 40 kg N	4.0 a	3.8	3.8	78.9 b	76.8 a	81.4 a
PU @ 80 kg N	5.3 bc	5.0 a	5.0 a	94.1 c	95.8 abc	97.3 ab
PU @ 120 kg N	5.8 cd	5.9 b	6.1 b	103.7 cd	111.7 bcd	107.5 ab
S + USG 1 WT	5.2 b	5.0 a	4.9 a	70.4 ab	89.5 ab	91.3 ab
S + USG 2 WT	6.4	6.0 b	6.5 b	124.8 e	111.7 bcd	118.1 b
S + USG 3 WT	5.8 cd	5.9 ab	6.3 b	97.8 cd	121.5 cd	109.5 b
S + USG 4 WT	5.9 d	6.0 b	6.2 b	111.4 de	129.5 d	117.5 b
S + USG 5 WT	6.0 d	5.7 b	5.9 b	110.1 de	97.3 ab	103.1 ab
CD at 5%	0.50	0.59	0.71	15.0	26.7	27.1
<i>r</i> to panicle number	0.893**	0.918**	0.943**	-	-	-
<i>r</i> to wet soil ammonium N						
15 DT	-	0.702*	0.626	-	0.666*	0.666*
30 DT	-	0.702*	0.888**	-	0.662	0.879**
45 DT	-	0.807**	0.853**	-	0.838**	0.823**
60 DT	-	0.938**	0.928**	-	0.936**	0.905**

^a * and ** = significance at P = 0.05 and P = 0.01, respectively. Values followed by the same letter in a column do not differ significantly. ^b PU was applied as split applications (50% at transplanting, 25% at tillering, and 25% at panicle initiation); USG was applied at 29 kg N/ha at 10.12 cm depth; S = *Sesbania aculeata* grown in situ for 55 d; + N content of 0.49% in 1987-88, 0.51% in 1988-89, and 0.51% in 1989-90.

Table 2. Grain yield and N uptake (grain + straw) of residual wheat, nitrate production at wheat planting, and available soil N at the end of the experiment ^a. Pantnagar, U. P., India. 1987-90.

Treatment ^b	Grain yield (t/ha)			N uptake (kg/ha)		
	1987-88	1988-89	1989-90	1987-88	1988-89	1988-90
Control	0.9 a	1.0 a	1.2 a	23.5 a	29.8 a	28.3 a
PU @ 40 kg N	0.9 a	1.0 a	1.2 a	25.4 ab	31.4 ab	28.9 a
PU @ 80 kg N	0.9 a	1.0 a	1.3 a	27.5 abc	30.2 a	31.7 a
PU @ 120 kg N	0.9 a	1.1 a	1.2 a	30.2 bcd	31.7 ab	32.1 a
S + USG 1 WT	1.2 b	1.9 b	1.9 b	34.5 d	37.5 bc	42.1 b
S + USG 2 WT	1.2 b	1.7 b	1.9 b	27.5 abc	43.6 c	48.1 b
S + USG 3 WT	1.2 b	1.6 b	1.7 b	33.2 d	39.5 c	45.1 b
S + USG 4 WT	1.2 b	1.7 b	1.8 b	29.8 bcd	43.5 c	47.2 b
S + USG 5 WT	1.0 b	1.9 b	1.8 b	29.5 bcd	39.5 c	46.1 b
CD at 5%	0.29	0.34	0.41	5.41	6.12	7.30
<i>r</i> to nitrate production at wheat planting in respective years	0.921**	0.964**	0.960**	0.738**	0.920**	0.943**
	Nitrate N			Available soil N (kg/ha) (1990)		
	1987-88	1988-89	1989-90			
Control	14.2	17.1	12.8	264		
PU @ 40 kg N	14.9	16.1	13.4	270		
PU @ 80 kg N	15.7	19.1	13.0	270		
PU @ 120 kg N	14.9	20.1	14.1	283		
S + USG 1 WT	23.4	27.6	24.8	295		
S + USG 2 WT	20.8	29.3	22.5	293		
S + USG 3 WT	20.1	26.5	23.1	301		
S + USG 4 WT	22.5	27.2	25.7	286		
S + USG 5 WT	20.1	29.1	25.1	298		
Mean	18.51	23.57	19.38	284.4		

^a ** = significant at P = 0.01, ^b All treatments were applied to the rice crop only. Nitrate N and available soil N were determined for each treatment from combined sample of three replications.

after transplanting (WT) gave about the same yield as that of 120 kg N/ha applied as PU. Yields obtained with 120 kg N/ha as PU and Sesbania + USG@ 2-5 WT were significantly more than those with 80 kg N/ha as PU. Yield obtained with Sesbania + USG@ 1 WT was equal to that with 80 kg N/ha through PU. Grain yields had significant positive correlations with panicle number and with soil ammonium N measured during 1988-89 and 1989-90 at different rice growth stages (Table 1). N uptake by rice showed a trend similar to that of yield obtained.

Integrated management of Sesbania + USG@ 1-5 WT in lowland rice resulted in a significant increase in residual wheat yields compared with the control and with PU applied to rice at 40, 80, or 120 kg N/ha (Table 2). Increase in yield was greater in the second year and N uptake by the residual wheat crop was greater in the third year, and were significantly correlated with soil nitrate at wheat planting. Integrated GM + USG in rice - wheat rotation helped to maintain higher available soil N after 3 yr compared with the control and with PU application to the rice crop (Table 2).

Integrated N management with Sesbania GM and USG@ 2-4 WT can be used instead of PU at the recommended dose in a rice - wheat rotation where there is only time enough to grow a Sesbania crop for 50-60 d before transplanting rice. Using a renewable N source in lowland rice also benefits the succeeding wheat crop in a rice - wheat rotation, is equivalent to 20-30 kg N/ha, and will help to sustain soil N fertility. ■

Effects of gypsum, farmyard manure, and N on ameliorating highly sodic soil and on yields of rice and wheat

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We explored the possibility of reducing the dose of gypsum application in conjunction with applying farmyard manure (FYM) and at two N levels. The field experiment was conducted from

Effect of soil amendments and N on grain yield of rice and wheat in a sodic soil.

Treatment	Grain yield (t/ha)							
	Rice				Wheat			
	1989	1990	1991	Pooled	1989-90	1990-91	1991-92	Pooled
Amendment								
Control	3.0	4.6	5.2	4.3	0.2	1.0	1.2	0.8
Gypsum @ 25% GR	5.1	5.3	5.3	5.2	1.7	2.2	2.3	2.1
Gypsum @ 50% GR	5.4	5.5	5.3	5.4	2.0	2.3	2.4	2.2
Farmyard manure (FYM) @ 20 Mg/ha	4.1	5.2	5.3	4.9	1.4	2.0	2.2	1.9
Gypsum @ 25% GR + FYM @ 20 Mg/ha	5.8	5.8	5.8	5.8	2.1	2.8	2.8	2.6
Gypsum @ 50% GR + FYM @ 20 Mg/ha	6.1	6.0	5.9	6.0	2.4	2.8	2.9	2.7
LSD at P = 0.05	0.3	0.4	0.4	0.4	0.4	0.4	0.3	0.4
N								
100 kg/ha	4.7	5.2	5.4	5.1	1.5	2.0	2.2	1.9
150 kg/ha	5.2	5.6	5.6	5.4	1.8	2.3	2.5	2.2
LSD at P = 0.05	0.2	0.2	0.3	0.2	0.2	0.2	0.2	0.2

Effect of amendments on pH and exchangeable sodium percentage (ESP) of sodic soil profile after a 3-yr rice - wheat sequence.

○—○ = control,
 □—□ = FYM,
 ●—● = Gypsum
 25% GR, △—△ =
 Gypsum 50% GR,
 ▲—▲ = Gypsum
 25% GR + FYM,
 ◻—◻ = Gypsum
 50% GR + FYM.

1989 to 1990 at CSSRI's Gudha experimental farm on a highly sodic soil with sand + silt 85.4%, clay 14.6%, CaCO₃ 3.4%, organic C 0.20%, pH 10.4, exchangeable sodium percentage (ESP) 89, cation exchange capacity (CEC) 10 meq/100 g soil, gypsum requirement 25 t/ha, available N 45/kg ha, Olsen's extractable P 38 kg/ha, NH₄OAC extractable K 478 kg/ha, and DTPA extractable Zn 0.42 mg/kg.

The experiment was laid out in a split-plot design with 4 replications of 12 treatment combinations. Treatments were a control (no amendment); gypsum @ 25% gypsum requirement (GR) of soil (6.25 t/ha); gypsum @ 50% GR (12.5 t/ha); FYM @ 20 t/ha; gypsum @ 25%

GR + FYM @ 20 t/ha; gypsum @ 50% GR + FYM @ 20 t/ha, and two levels of N (100 and 150 kg/ha).

Gypsum and FYM treatments were applied in one dose 10 d before transplanting rice in 1989. Farmyard manure contained 0.85% N, 0.35% P, 0.78% K, 0.35% Ca, 0.24% Mg, 0.22% S, 52 ppm Zn, 125 ppm Mn, and 320 ppm Fe. Plots were irrigated and 30-d-old seedlings of rice variety Jaya transplanted on 21 Jul 1989, 5 Jul 1990, and 14 Jul 1991. The crop was harvested at maturity in October. Subsequently, wheat variety HD2329 was sown on 25 Nov 1989, 19 Nov 1990, and 18 Nov 1991. The crop was harvested at maturity in April of the following year.

Both crops received N (as per treatments) in three splits: one-third at transplanting of rice/sowing of wheat and the rest in two equal splits at 3 and 6 wk of crop growth. A basal dose of 40 kg ZnSO₄/ha was applied to rice in the rotation. The soil tested high in available P and K so these elements were not applied.

Results showed that gypsum and FYM improved significantly the grain yield of rice and wheat (see table) and substantially decreased pH and ESP of the soil profile (see figure) compared with the control. When gypsum dose was reduced from 50 to 25% of GR, with or without FYM, there was no significant decrease in the yield of either crop except rice during 1989. Gypsum @ 25% GR + FYM was significantly better than gypsum @ 50% GR and at par with gypsum @ 50% GR + FYM in decreasing soil pH and ESP and improving crop yields. Increasing N dose from 100 to 150 kg/ha significantly improved the yield of both crops. Interaction between N and other treatments, however, was not significant.

Based on pooled analysis of the data, it is suggested that gypsum @ 25% GR with FYM @ 20 t/ha could be recommended to successfully ameliorate sodic soils and to maximize rice and wheat production. ■